

Fischer, M. (2019). Challenges of pre-vocational education and training and vocational orientation. In F. Marhuenda & M.J. Chisvert-Tarazona (Eds.), *Pedagogical concerns and market demands in VET. Proceedings of the 3rd Crossing Boundaries in VET conference, Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp. 102-106) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2641093>

Challenges of pre-vocational education and training and vocational orientation

Fischer, Martin

Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, m.fischer@kit.edu

Abstract

The paper presents concepts for vocational orientation in the general education system and for vocational preparation in vocational schools, which have been tested in several research and development projects. At the core of all projects is the attempt to stimulate self-activity of adolescents that goes beyond mere information and matching processes. Above all, the paper presents theoretical foundations of a didactic conception, with the help of which young people are supported in the development of ‘vocational biography design competence’ in the career entry phase, so that they can (better) master status passages and risk situations during their professional life.

Keywords

vocational orientation; occupational guidance; matching approach; vocational biography design competence

1 Transition problems of young adolescents

In most European countries it is a problem for young people to enter an apprenticeship or a study program which directly leads to a desired occupation. Even in Germany, where the youth unemployment rate is comparably low, 200.000 – 300.000 young people find themselves every year in the so-called transition system (BMBF 2016, p. 56), where it is not possible to obtain a qualification for a formally recognized occupation. Therefore, in Germany and in many other European countries programs for vocational orientation (organized within general education) and pre-vocational education and training (organized by vocational schools or labour market institutions) are being established in order to offer occupational guidance.

Mostly, this occupational guidance is explicitly or implicitly driven by a matching approach. The question is posed: Which occupation fits you most? And if this question is answered, e.g. with the help of vocational aptitude tests, people are put into boxes, based on typologies like those of Holland (1985): You are the technical type, you are the entrepreneurial type, etc.

Although on one hand it seems to be necessary trying to help young people into their first apprenticeship or study program it is on the other hand not sufficient. Today's (working) life is characterized by upheavals and changes (e. g. high drop-out rates in apprenticeships and study programs (BMBF 2016, 2017), precarious working conditions): Lifelong learning instead of a lifelong occupation. With the erosion of the “normal work biography” not only the first career choice, but also the handling of these changes in the further professional and private life becomes more and more important. This was the starting point of several of our research and development projects for the development of didactic concepts of extended career orientation. The current vocational orientation should be extended beyond one-time

decisions on vocational choices to the direction of active and continuous shaping of one's professional biography.

2 Didactical concepts for strengthening biographical work of young people

Many of our learning-/teaching-arrangements are based on an adaption of so-called developmental tasks after Havighurst (1948) and are oriented towards the concept of vocational biography design (Hendrich 2003). Developmental tasks are tasks which everybody has to accomplish in different phases of her/his life (e. g. separation from parents, finding a job, develop partnership, find a political orientation etc.), but can be interpreted and realized differently by the individual. Those developmental tasks are used within learning-/teaching-arrangements and are interlinked with aspirations and decisions towards one's professional biography.

2.1 Analysing and testing professional work

In a current research and development project "Strengthening self-management and self-learning competence in the transition from school to work and training", funded by the state of Baden-Württemberg, students of the transition system are to determine an in-company learning task for themselves in an obligatory company internship, carry it out and reflect on the experience gained.

The project focuses on the importance of internships for career choice decisions (cf. e. g. Bergzog 2011, p. 8). However, the work tasks assigned to the interns are often randomly selected, so that the interns sometimes have little job-typical work to do (making coffee, copying, cleaning the workshop, etc.). Couldn't we pay more attention to occupation-specific work activities being carried out in the internship and which (more active) role the young people themselves can take on?

This question is taken up by the research and development project outlined here and gives the young people a joint responsibility to pay attention to the type of work tasks they carry out in the internship. This is relatively demanding for students in the transition system and they are prepared accordingly. For this purpose, the so-called BAG analysis (Analysis of Occupational Tasks, see Reinhold et al. 2003, Fischer 2014) has been adapted for students in the transition system: The young people are instructed to select and then carry out an in-company learning task that is typical of the occupation, open to different solutions and corresponds to a complete action of work (planning, acting, evaluating).

Interim results are encouraging: Young people in the transition system learn to pay better attention to whether and how work tasks in specific occupations correspond to their interests and what skills are required to carry out these tasks.

2.2 Developing an understanding of technology and shaping technology

Since 1991 until today (cf. KMK 2015, p. 2), the framework agreement on vocational schools of the German Conference of Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs has emphasised the students' competences "to shape the world of work and society in social and ecological responsibility" as a guiding principle for vocational training (based on an original idea of Rauner (1985)).

In the project "MediaArt@Edu", funded by the German Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF), this guiding idea in vocational preparation was revived. Here the didactical concept is related to media design processes in order to open up new concrete possibilities for action and spaces of experience for young people. Young people in the vocational preparation phase used open tasks to design, construct and program project ideas with different media technologies (Robotics, Light Design, GamesLab, Sound Designing,

Smart Textile), visualize them in a personal portfolio, reflect on them, explain them in an “explanatory video” and present them (Reimann & Bekk 2016).

As was shown in the project evaluation (round table reflection and interviews), young people are by no means automatically aware of their own abilities. What was learned in the workshops was usually not recognised or not linked to a professional benefit (“I want to become a cook, I don't need to learn to build a robot for that”). Therefore, it was necessary to initiate reflection processes in order to gain awareness about what they had learned and its usability for professional purposes. The portfolio method could be used as a stimulus for this.

2.3 Develop a vision of one's own future

When discussing the question of how to didactically promote the development of vocational biographical design competence, the idea arose of confronting students with situations in which they could playfully try out this "balancing" between the characteristics and interests of the learner on the one hand and the respective social possibility and requirement structures on the other hand. A board game (“My way!”) was developed in which the students deal with life situations and information that are relevant in the 15-30 age range (Fischer et al. 2015). Some of the life situations themselves were taken from the longitudinal study “Status Passages and Risk Passages in the Life Course” (Heinz et al. 2004). As part of the data evaluation of this longitudinal study, the BARB model of self-socialisation was also developed. It represents one of the theoretical bases for the development of the board game "My Way!" Based on the question of how the actors deal with the (external and internal) limitations and possibilities of their (occupational) life course design, the use of a person's scope for interpretation and action is divided into four steps: 1) To **balance** (where do I stand?), 2) to develop **aspirations** (where do I want to go?), 3) to **realise** them (how can I do that?) and 4) to **balance** the result again (what has that brought me?). We regard it as an essential content of vocational biographical design competence to be able to consciously undertake these four steps and thus gain subjective potential for action.

Following on from the development tasks in adolescence, life-important areas were defined for young people in the vocational orientation phase, which are discussed by the players in the game "My Way!" In the areas of “occupation”, “school”, “friendship”, “family”, “partnership” and “my well-being”, the groups work together on tasks that are important for vocational orientation or reorientation. The aim of the board game is to sensitise people to the upheavals that may occur in their lives.

The playful coping with (imagined) life situations is linked with information about occupations: Information on up to 80 occupations is contained. The game also addresses the topic of migration (protagonists in the life situations depicted are often people with a migration background) and gender issues (e. g. through the topic “Men in women's occupations”). The response in the tests to date with about 100 students has been positive, but a comprehensive evaluation of the effects of this form of vocational orientation (the game has been distributed to all schools in Baden-Württemberg except the gymnasium) is still lacking.

2.4 Working on one's own biography

In the European project “A European concept to visualize and reflect the vocational biography using digital media”, curricular modules and scenarios for a European course on the visualization of vocational biographical design competence using digital media are being developed, tested with young people in vocational preparation measures in six countries and evaluated (Reimann & Huber 2016).

Based on the question of how the theoretical construct of “vocational biographical design competence” can be operationalised in lessons with young people, the students of vocational preparation courses developed the topic of vocational biography design visually. Against the

background of the young people's activities in the social media, self-presentation on the Internet ("My digital self") played a particularly important role: the starting point was to think about how I as a person am portrayed on the Internet. The following questions were raised and the visual material found was then used to research the web: Status of one's own self-presentation: How am I depicted on the Net? How do I evaluate this picture? How would I like to present myself on the net?

The students identified an object or a photo that represents them in their opinion (e. g. skateboard, T-shirt ...). The objects and photos were then included in the photo session: With the help of digital photography and performative expression, the young people answered four questions in a pictorial way and "brought them into the picture" in the truest sense of the word:

- What is my strength (my gold)?
- What is my hobby?
- Who is my role model?
- What would I like to know more about?

Answering these questions required detailed discussion and explanation in previously formed working groups. Young people who could not name a strength were supported by their classmates. The students also wrote a text "About me" to add biographical elements and to express the photographic portrait linguistically. The results were compiled in a photo book with all the students' work and could be used for application purposes.

3 Summary and conclusion

Due to the erosion of the 'normal work biography' there is a need for extended vocational orientation for all young people, including high school students, in the sense described above. This need can be assumed for reasons of personality development alone, because the requirements of career biography design affect everyone, and probably not just once in a lifetime, meaning

- To make decisions in which one's own expectations with regard to career planning are balanced against the actual or supposed expectations of others (e. g. father, mother, friends, social stereotypes),
- To associate one's own development opportunities and desires with one's own current starting conditions (e. g. action skills, school grades, certificates of graduation, application skills) and in doing so to
- Take into account one's own interests, aspirations and competences as well as the type and number of vocational training opportunities available.

This need for vocational orientation is additionally supported by the increasing diversification of (educational) paths. However, it cannot then be a reasonable goal of sorting in young people aged 15 or 16 somewhere by means of vocational orientation. This is evidently not successful anyway, as the current average age at entry to vocational education and training of over 19 years in Germany and the high drop-out rates show. Rather, the aim is to support young people and young adults in coping better with status passages and risk situations throughout their educational and working lives.

References

- Bergzog, T. (2011). Das Betriebspraktikum als Instrument schulischer Berufsorientierung. *bwp@*, Spezial 5. Retrieved from http://www.bwpat.de/ht2011/ft02/bergzog_ft02-ht2011.pdf.
- BMBF – Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (2016). *Berufsbildungsbericht 2016*. Bonn, Berlin. Retrieved from https://www.bmbf.de/pub/Berufsbildungsbericht_2016.pdf.
- BMBF – Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (2017). *Pressemitteilung 057/2017*.
- Fischer, M. (2014). Von der Arbeitsanalyse zur Planung beruflicher Bildung. Eine berufspädagogische Lehrveranstaltung im Kontext „forschenden Lernens“. In Spöttl, G., Becker, M., & Fischer, M. (Eds.). *Arbeitsforschung und berufliches Lernen* (pp. 93–117). Frankfurt am Main et al.: Peter Lang.
- Fischer, M., Stoewe, K., Barkholz, S., Ziegler, M. & Kampa, C. (2015). „My Way! Finde deinen Weg“ – ein didaktisches Konzept der schulischen Berufsorientierung als Beitrag zur Förderung berufsbiografischer Gestaltungskompetenz. *bwp@* Nr. 27. Retrieved from http://www.bwpat.de/ausgabe27/fischer_etal_bwpat27.pdf.
- Havighurst, R. J. (1948). *Developmental tasks and education*. New York: Longman
- Heinz, W. R., Kühn, T., & Witzel, A. (2004). A life-course perspective on work-related learning. In Fischer, M., Boreham, N., & Nyhan, B. (Eds.). *European perspectives on learning at work: the acquisition of work process knowledge* (pp. 196–215). Luxemburg: Office for Official Publications for the European Communities.
- Hendrich, W. (2003). *Berufsbiographische Gestaltungskompetenz*. Unveröffentlichte Habilitationsschrift. Flensburg: University
- Holland, J. (1985). *Making vocational choices* (2nd ed.) Odessa, FL.: Psychological Assessment Resources, Inc.
- KMK – Sekretariat der Kultusministerkonferenz (2015). *Rahmenvereinbarung über die Berufsschule*. Retrieved from http://www.kmk.org/fileadmin/Dateien/veroeffentlichungen_beschluesse/2015/2015_03_12-RV-Berufsschule.pdf.
- Rauner, F. (1985). Technik und Bildung. *diskurs 10*. Arbeit und Technik. Problemfelder, Gestaltungsorte, Akteure (pp. 110–131). Bremen: University.
- Reimann, D., Bekk, S. & Fischer, M. (Eds.) (2016). *Gestaltungsorientierte Aktivierung von Lernenden. Übergänge in Schule – Ausbildung – Beruf*. Norderstedt: BoD.
- Reimann, D. & Huber, K. (2016). A European concept to visualize and reflect the vocational biography using digital media. In Reimann, D. Bekk, S. & Fischer, M. (Eds.). *Gestaltungsorientierte Aktivierung von Lernenden: Übergänge in Schule – Ausbildung – Beruf* (pp. 145-174). Norderstedt: BoD.
- Reinhold, M. et al (2003). *Curriculum-Design II: Entwickeln von Lernfeldern. Von beruflichen Arbeitsaufgaben zum Berufsbildungsplan*. Konstanz: Christiani.

Biographical note

Dr Martin Fischer is Professor for Vocational Pedagogy at Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (Research University in the German State of Baden-Württemberg).